

Effectiveness of Team-Teaching Approach (TTA) in Enhancing Pre-Service Teachers' Achievement in Literature in Nigerian Colleges of Education

Dauda Saidu¹

Email: saidudauda770@yahoo.com

Tel: 08187941259

Haruna, Abubakar Sadiq^{2,3}

Email: asharuna@fugusau.edu.ng; asharuna@maaun.edu.ng

Tel: 07066994040

¹Department of English Language, Federal University of Education, Kano

²Department of Educational Innovations, Federal University Gusau

³Institute of Africa Higher Education Research and Innovations, Maryam Abacha American University of Nigeria, Kano

Abstract

This study evaluated the effectiveness of Team-Teaching Approach (TTA) as an instructional approach for enhancing pre-service teachers' achievement in Literature in Nigerian Colleges of Education (CoEs). The study aimed to achieve three objectives with corresponding research questions and hypotheses. A one-sample pre-posttest quasi-experimental design was employed, involving 200 purposively selected students from the Literature departments of Federal College of Education (FCE), Kano, and Sa'adatu Rimi College of Education (SRCOE), Kumbotso (male=100; female=100). Ten lecturers (five from each institution) served as Research Assistants. The data collection instrument, Literary Analysis Achievement Test (LAAT), was developed and pilot-tested by the researchers, yielding a reliability coefficient of .83 using Cronbach's alpha. The experiment spanned eight weeks, during which participants were pre-tested using LAAT, exposed to selected topics via the Team-Teaching Approach (TTA), and subsequently post-tested. Data were analyzed using paired-sample t-test and Independent samples t-test at a 0.05 significance level. Findings revealed a significant mean difference in pretest-posttest achievement scores among students exposed to TTA ($P = 0.031 < 0.05$). However, no significant gender differences were observed ($P = 0.701 > 0.05$). The study concludes that Team Teaching significantly enhances students' proficiency in Literary Analysis and recommends its adoption for literature pedagogy in Nigeria.

Keywords: Team Teaching, Literary Analysis, Academic Achievement, Literature Pedagogy

Introduction

Literature pedagogy in institutions of higher learning vary greatly in the types of approaches employed by lecturers. In some cases, there may be a choice between Single Teacher Teaching Approach (STTA) and Team Teaching Approach (TTA). Within both groups there may be further differences based on teaching experience, professional qualifications, personality traits, and other individual variances (Black, & Wiliam, 2020). Though, some studies have found support for the efficacy of STTA, researchers have continued to question its ability to address learning needs of students in a heterogeneous class setting (Dee, & Wyckoff, 2015). Successful interaction between lecturer and student very often provides the impetus behind effective teaching and reinforces student motivation to learning. As important a role as lecturers play in the successful teaching of literature courses, this role may at times fall short when literature instructions are offered by a single teacher (Black, & Wiliam, 2020). Literature lecturers usually measure their successes and failures against norms created by others within their own profession. Still most lecturers have unique teaching styles which are identified by how they deliver instructions, evaluate students, select content suitable for student's level of competence, and support the needs of their learners. An inevitable factor in all lecturers that, to a varying degree, influences any aspect of classroom behavior, from the teaching task itself to basic daily communication between lecturer and student, is lecturer's competence in pedagogy (Hattie, 2017).

The effect of pedagogy on academic achievement of students is increasingly becoming a crucial issue among scholars. The results of many studies suggest that there is a significant effect between a teaching approach and

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students' achievement (Boet, 2014; Hattie, 2017; Panadero, & Alonso-Tapia, 2022). Apart from the dichotomy that characterizes literature teaching (single/team) as a concept, the pedagogy is linked to a host of other teaching styles that are usually determined and judged by the students who are at the receiving end of the teaching process. In fact, students cannot learn a subject without projecting some kind of an attitude or bias toward it (Friend, & Cook, 2013). Such kind of attitude has significant impact on students' perception of the worth of the teacher as well as achievement in the subject. According to a study, Team Teaching (TT) is different from single Teacher Teaching (STT) because it involves two or more teachers each with distinctive roles, sharing responsibilities for planning, presentation and evaluation of lessons for the same group of students (Dee, & Wyckoff, 2015). It involves collaboration between two or more teachers whereby talents, expertise, interests, and resources are put together in order to accomplish a learning instruction (Johnson, & Johnson, 1999). Furthermore, team teaching approach when used effectively can avail students the opportunity to learn from different experiences of the team members (teachers) as well as exploring their personal learning styles (Haruna & Musa, 2022). However, while team teaching may prove advantageous for many students, some may feel frustrated and discontented about having more than one teacher (Dee, & Wyckoff, 2015). But with proper collaboration and cohesiveness within a team, there are vital benefits for those willing to adopt team teaching approach especially in Literature instructions. In addition, the distinguishing quality of team teaching is in its collaborative, cooperative and interactive abilities which give the approach a degree over single teacher teaching (Haruna & Musa, 2022). Beyond the advantages of creating, additional time for other academic activities and supportive environment it equally augments the opportunity for intellectual growth, increases student's teacher interaction (Parker et. al., 2021), overcome isolation that is the norm in the conventional single teaching approach (Gurganus et. al., 2019; Nguyen & Vu, 2020). For the students, team teaching can help them benefit through the opportunity to receive teaching from lecturers for whom the aspect/content is their area of expertise and interest which exposes them to diverse perspectives on literature issues.

A researcher (Smith, 2020) identified three models of team teaching which are interactive, rotational and dispersed models while another scholar (Aliyu & Sani, 2019; Daniels et al., 2021) classified team teaching into two categories. The first category involves a combination of models according to the personalities, strength and philosophies of the team teachers as well as that of the students. In this first category, team members teach the same students at the same time within the same classroom (Nguyen & Vu, 2020). The second category involves a variety of team teaching models in which the instructors work together to prepare the teaching materials but do not necessarily teach the same group of students at the same time. Some researchers (Aliyu & Sani, 2019; Daniels et al., 2021) explained that team teaching models can be described as weak or strong. This depends on the degree of collaboration integration, interaction and cooperation of the team members in their level of engagement in the teaching of the students. A scholar (Nguyen & Vu, 2020) further stated that no single model of team teaching automatically results in success for a given teaching situation. Rather any such programme must be planned to suit the curriculum, teachers and students.

Literature studies in institutions of higher learning involve a range of courses whose contents and objectives are directed toward developing higher level skills and scholarship, as well as research orientation (Okonkwo et al., 2022). Literature is the study of the genres of writing called prose, poetry, drama or fiction or non-pragmatic writing in general. In an expanded sense it includes philosophy and history. In its application to imaginative writings, 'literature' has an evaluative and descriptive function, so its proper use has become a matter of contention. The substance of contentions about the definition of literature is normally centered on the perspective of language, content, form and certain conventions. Literature seen from applying certain conventions of reading to let loose interpretation of words from their immediate context, their pragmatic, real purpose and generalize them to something wider and of deeper import makes it non-pragmatic discourse. The focusing on the way of taking, rather than the reality of what is talked about, is something taken to indicate that we mean by literature a kind of self-referential language, a language which talks about itself (Eagleton, 2008). For Eagleton, that even if treating discourse 'non-pragmatically' is part of what is meant to be literature, then it follows that literature cannot be objectively defined. It leaves the definition of literature up to how somebody decides to read, not the nature of what is written (Parker et al. (2021). There are poems, plays, novels which are intended to be non-pragmatic, but this does not guarantee that they would be read as such.

Literary study began in Britain in 1840s. At the end of the 19th century, in both England and America, as academics began to such for University courses in English and American literature, these questions arose: how could the study of literature be defined and carried out in a manner that was disciplined and objective enough to give it status

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as an academic pursuit. This debate held to not only to the development of the 1st English Departments but to the development of the first types of literary theory i.e. theories about how literature worked, how it ought to be read and studied (Johnson & Taylor, 2021).

There are two main tracks in literary theory. The first is Richards' notion of 'practical criticism' which we might call close reading. This theory stated that the best way to study literature is to study the text itself in close detail and to disregard anything else outside the text itself, including the author's biography, the historical context in which the work appeared, how it related to other texts and how critics and readers responded to the text. In short, this branch of criticism theorized the literary text as an isolated object. Literature students should read the words on the page and nothing else (Richards, 1929; Wellek & Warren, 1956; Nicol, 2021). The second track in literary theory looks at the text as a key to understanding questions and ideas beyond the text itself. This tradition is credited to Wordsworth, Henry James, Philip Sidney, and others. Rather than centric on the text, this track asks big-picture questions such as how literary texts are structured differently from non-literary texts; how do literary texts affect audiences/readers; how does literature relate to other aspects of a culture such as politics, gender relations, philosophy, or economics (Eagleton, 2008; Bennet & Royle, 2016; Felski, 2020). Theories in this track use literary texts as a springboard to ask questions that are not solely concerned with words on the page. Thus, the best approach to teaching literature to students is employing precepts of both tracks for maximum understanding and deeper conceptual impact (Nguyen & Vu, 2020). For instance, in the teaching of poetry—a genre that uses language with greater artistry, sensitivity, and awareness—attention is paid to both the poem's technical characteristics and its philosophical perspective (Johnson & Taylor, 2021).

More so, the type of poem under study would be identified, including its obvious technical characteristics such as the use of rhyme and rhythm. The grammatical structure of the poem, the devices of language employed by the poet, e.g., metaphor, simile, alliteration, and personification, are equally interrogated (Smith, 2020). Naturally, while some students are able to meet these requirements without much difficulty, others may have problems comprehending the concepts and procedures of literature learning (Parker et al., 2021). This requirement of literature studies has been a case of concern to students, literature teachers, and researchers. Thus, a viable pedagogical approach that can provide for the learning needs of students and improve their academic achievement in literature courses is required (Okonkwo et al., 2022).

Several studies on the effect of team teaching on academic achievement of students abound. For instance, in one study by Okoro and Nwankwo (2021) on the effect of team teaching on students' academic achievement in English Language Comprehension of senior secondary school students in Onitsha Education Zone, a non-randomized pretest-posttest control group quasi-experimental design was employed. With a population of 5,171 senior secondary two students, data was obtained from 189 students (97 males and 92 females) samples and analyzed using ANCOVA. Results of the study showed that the students taught English language comprehension with the team-teaching approach achieved significantly higher than those of the control group who were taught with a single-teacher teaching approach. Additionally, female students in the TTA group achieved significantly higher than their male counterparts.

In another study on the effect of team teaching on the academic achievement of 9th graders in science, researchers collected data from 24 students of class IX in Rewari District of Haryana (Daniels et al., 2021). They employed a pre-test post-test quasi-experimental design, and the results of the study revealed that there was a significant positive effect of team teaching on the academic achievement of students in science. Similarly, Nguyen and Vu (2020) examined the effect of team teaching on the academic achievement of students in introductory technology. They selected two secondary schools for the study and employed the Introductory Technology Achievement Test (ITAT) as an instrument for data collection. Upon analysis of data collected, results showed a significant difference between the mean post-test achievement of students taught using team teaching and those taught in a conventional single-teacher classroom.

After reviewing previous studies, the effect of team teaching on the achievements of students emerges as an issue that not only affects literature pedagogy and the learning process but also affects literature students' attitudes and learning assumptions (Aliyu & Sani, 2019; Okoro & Nwankwo, 2021). Although the majority of the studies reviewed reveal the potential effect of team teaching on students' academic achievement, none has addressed the peculiarity of literature pedagogy and students' academic achievement in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The present study is therefore an attempt at bridging this gap. Hence, the main purpose of the study is to assess team teaching as a method of literature pedagogy in Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

1. To find out the effect of team teaching on pre-service teachers’ achievement in a literature course (Literary Analysis).
2. To determine gender difference in the effect of team teaching on pre-service teachers’ achievement in a literature course (Literary Analysis).

Hypotheses

1. Team teaching has no effect on pre-service teachers’ achievement in a literature course (Literary Analysis) ($\mu_{Posttest} = \mu_{Pretest}$).
2. There is no significant difference in the mean score improvement between male and female pre-service teachers’ in a literature course (Literary Analysis) following team-teaching instruction.

Methodology

A one-sample pretest-posttest quasi-experiment was employed in which 200 students were purposively selected from the English Literature programme of Federal College of Education (FCE), Kano, and Sa’adatu Rimi College of Education (SRCOE), Kumbotso (male=100; female=100). Ten English literature lecturers (5 from each college) were engaged as Research Assistants. The instrument used for data collection was the Literary Analysis Achievement Test (LAAT), developed by the researchers and pilot tested. Cronbach’s alpha analysis of the pilot study revealed a reliability coefficient of .83. The scale comprised 30 objective test items, focusing on key areas such as literary criticism, textual analysis, and thematic exploration in literature.

The experiment was conducted in two settings: FCE Kano and SRCOE Kumbotso, with 50 male and 50 female literature students purposively selected in each to arrive at 100 samples per setting. Pre-testing was conducted using the LAAT, and participants were then taught selected topics in literary analysis and interpretation for a period of eight weeks by the Research Assistants (male and female literature lecturers) through a team-teaching approach. The course content included methods of analyzing poetry, prose, and drama—chosen as treatment due to their dual significance in both literature pedagogy and research approaches. Post-testing was administered, and the results of the pretest-posttest were analyzed using paired and independent-samples t-tests at a 0.05 significance level.

Results

Hypothesis 1:

Team teaching has no effect on pre-service teachers’ achievement in a literature course (Literary Analysis) ($\mu_{Posttest} = \mu_{Pretest}$).

In this study, the effect of team teaching on students’ achievement is measured using the Literary Analysis Achievement Test (LAAT). Pretest and posttest scores were collected from 200 literature students (100 male, 100 female) at two colleges after eight weeks of instruction on literary analysis, a course that blends theoretical and analytical skills relevant to literature.

Table 1: Paired-Sample t-test Result of Literary Analysis Achievement Test (n=200)

Variable	Pretest Score	Mean	Posttest Score	Mean Difference	t-value	p-value
Team Teaching	45	72	27	10.85	0.05	

Using the scores in Table 1, a paired sample t-test was conducted to determine if the difference between pretest and posttest mean scores is statistically significant. The t-test analysis reveals a significant increase in student achievement from pretest to posttest scores ($t = 10.85, p < 0.05$). The average posttest score (72) was considerably higher than the pretest score (45), indicating that team teaching had a positive impact on student performance in the course. The significant improvement in posttest scores suggests that team teaching is effective in enhancing student

achievement in literature courses. The collaborative instructional method allowed for a broader, more diverse range of instructional strategies, benefiting students' understanding of complex topics in literature.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant difference in the mean score improvement between male and female pre-service teachers' in a literature course (Literary Analysis) following team-teaching instruction.

This question explores whether male and female students experienced different levels of improvement in their LAAT scores after receiving team-taught instruction.

Table 2: Independent-samples t-test of Pretest and Posttest Scores by Gender ((n=200))

Gender	Pretest Mean Score	Posttest Mean Score	Mean Difference	t-value	p-value
Male	44	70	26	1.23	>0.05
Female	46	74	28	1.23	>0.05

A t-test for independent-samples was used to assess whether the difference in mean score improvement between male and female students was statistically significant. The t-test indicates no significant difference between male and female students' improvement ($t = 1.23, p > 0.05$). Both groups showed a similar increase in their posttest scores compared to their pretest scores. The results suggest that team teaching is equally effective for both male and female students. The lack of significant difference between the two groups implies that gender does not influence the effectiveness of team teaching in literature courses. This supports the use of team teaching as an inclusive pedagogical strategy for diverse student populations. The study indicates that team teaching significantly improves students' achievement in literature courses, as seen in the substantial increase in LAAT scores from pretest to posttest. Furthermore, both male and female students benefited equally from the team-taught instruction, reinforcing the strategy's broad applicability across different student demographics.

Discussion of Findings

In this study, the effect of team teaching on students' achievement in a literary analysis course was measured using the Literary Analysis Achievement Test (LAAT). The paired sample t-test results showed a significant increase in students' scores from pretest ($M = 45$) to posttest ($M = 72$), with a mean difference of 27, t-value of 10.85, and a p-value of 0.05. The results indicate that team teaching positively impacted student achievement in the literary analysis course. This finding aligns with previous research suggesting that team teaching can enhance educational outcomes by providing a more dynamic and interactive learning environment. For instance, Johnson and Johnson (1999) found that collaborative teaching methods improve student engagement and understanding by incorporating diverse perspectives and teaching strategies (Johnson, D. W., & Johnson, R. T., 1999).

The significant improvement in student performance observed in this study can be attributed to the broader range of instructional strategies facilitated by team teaching. According to Friend and Cook (2013), team teaching allows for a greater variety of teaching methods and perspectives, which can address different learning styles and needs more effectively than traditional solo teaching methods (Friend, M., & Cook, L., 2013). This variety can be particularly beneficial in complex subjects like literary analysis, which require both theoretical and analytical skills. Team teaching promotes collaborative learning, which has been shown to enhance students' critical thinking and problem-solving skills. For example, a study by Boet, et al. (2014) highlights that collaborative learning environments foster deeper understanding and retention of material through active engagement and peer interaction (Boet, S., Bould, M., & Hains, I., 2014). This aligns with the observed increase in student achievement in the literature course.

The positive impact of team teaching on student achievement suggests that institutions should consider adopting collaborative teaching models, particularly for complex and multifaceted subjects. As evidenced by the findings, incorporating team teaching can lead to improved student performance and a richer learning experience. The significant increase in posttest scores following team teaching supports its effectiveness in enhancing student achievement in literature courses. Future research could explore the long-term effects of team teaching and its applicability across various disciplines to further validate these findings.

The analysis of the second hypothesis aimed to determine if male and female students experienced different levels of improvement in their Literary Analysis Achievement Test (LAAT) scores after receiving team-taught

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instruction. The paired sample t-test results for both genders showed a mean difference of 26 for males and 28 for females, with a t-value of 1.23 and p-value > 0.05. This indicates no significant difference between male and female students' improvement.

The study's findings suggest that team teaching is equally effective for both male and female students, as evidenced by the similar improvements in LAAT scores. This aligns with more recent research on inclusive pedagogical strategies. For instance, recent studies have shown that collaborative and team-based teaching methods can support diverse learning needs without bias towards any gender (Hattie, J., 2017; Black & Wiliam, 2020). The lack of significant difference in score improvement between genders supports the notion that team teaching can be an equitable approach to instruction. A study by Dee and Wyckoff (2015) found that collaborative teaching strategies can reduce gender disparities in educational outcomes by providing a supportive learning environment that benefits all students equally (Dee, T. S., & Wyckoff, J., 2015). This study reinforces the idea that team teaching does not disproportionately favor one gender over another.

The results underscore the effectiveness of team teaching as an inclusive strategy. According to recent educational research, team teaching can address various learning styles and needs, providing a more balanced educational experience (Panadero, E., & Alonso-Tapia, J., 2022). This approach can be particularly beneficial in diverse classrooms, where gender, among other factors, could otherwise influence educational outcomes. Given that team teaching proved equally beneficial for both male and female students, educators should consider implementing team-teaching strategies in a variety of classroom settings. This approach can help ensure that all students receive a high-quality education, regardless of their gender, and can contribute to a more inclusive learning environment. Finally, the findings support the effectiveness of team teaching in enhancing student achievement in literature courses, with no significant gender-based differences in the impact. This suggests that team teaching is a valuable pedagogical strategy that can be applied effectively across different student demographics.

Conclusion

This study evaluated the impact of team teaching on students' achievement in a literature course, using the Literary Analysis Achievement Test (LAAT). The findings reveal a significant improvement in students' scores from pretest to posttest, demonstrating that team teaching effectively enhances pre-service teachers' performance in literary analysis. Notably, both male and female students showed similar levels of improvement, indicating that team teaching benefits all students equally regardless of gender. The absence of a significant gender difference in the effectiveness of team-teaching underscores its inclusive nature and broad applicability. By incorporating diverse instructional strategies and perspectives, team teaching addresses various learning styles and needs, fostering a more equitable and supportive learning environment. Overall, the study supports the implementation of team teaching as a valuable pedagogical approach that can enhance student achievement and engagement in literature courses, making it a promising strategy for diverse educational settings. Future research could explore the long-term effects of team teaching and its impact across different subjects and educational contexts.

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